

Spectrophotometric determination of neodymium(III), samarium(III) in micellar medium – An alternative to solvent extraction procedures

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Abstract : Complexation of neodymium(III) and samarium(III) with 1-(2-pyridyl azo)-2-naphthol (PAN) in the presence of surfactants was studied spectrophotometrically. PAN forms an intense red colored complex with Nd^{3+} , Sm^{3+} at pH 8.5-9.5 soluble in all the three micellar media. Absorption spectra of neodymium and samarium complexes were taken by optimizing conditions of interaction and chemical and analytical characteristics like pH, PAN concentrations and surfactant concentrations. Molar absorptivity of the complexes was found to be 4.4×10^4 , 6.2×10^4 , and $4.3 \times 10^4 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$ for Nd^{3+} and 5.8×10^4 , 7.4×10^4 , $5.7 \times 10^4 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$ for Sm^{3+} in CTAB, Triton-X and SDS respectively. Sensitivity was found to be 2.96×10^{-4} , 3.02×10^{-4} and $2.17 \times 10^{-4} \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ for Nd^{3+} and 2.37×10^{-4} , 1.8×10^{-4} , $2.37 \times 10^{-4} \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ for Sm^{3+} in CTAB, Triton-X and SDS. In all the three surfactants, sensitivity is greater than in the aqueous media. The relative standard deviation evaluated from ten independent determinations was 1.54, 0.514, 1.28 for Nd^{3+} and 1.51, .602, 1.29 for Sm^{3+} in CTAB, Triton-X and SDS. The detection limits obtained were 1.75, 1.8, 1.74 ppm for Nd^{3+} and 2.0, 2.5, 1.9 ppm for Sm^{3+} in CTAB, Triton-X and SDS. Effect of various ions on the determination of Nd^{3+} and Sm^{3+} were also studied so as to investigate the selectivity of the method.

Keywords : Spectrophotometry, micelles, neodymium, samarium, PAN.

Introduction

Solvent extraction techniques are widely used in the spectrophotometric determination of metal ions. However, organic solvents are expensive, toxic, and carcinogenic and cause environmental pollution. It is therefore important to develop methods that do not use solvent extraction. Surfactant molecules and micelles, designed as 'organized assemblies' exhibit several peculiar properties. They solubilize, concentrate and compartmentalize chemical species. They also alter dissociation constants, oxidation-reduction properties, provides unique reaction media and influence transport properties¹. Surfactants improve the analytical characteristics of chromophoric chelating organic reagents. Surfactants increase the sensitivity of the determination, decrease the equilibration time of the reaction, and increase the stability of the complex. Hence, the micellar solution can be used as a medium for spectrophotometric determination of metal ions²⁻⁶.

The importance of lanthanides in nuclear chemistry and metallurgy necessitated the development of methods

for their rapid determination and separations. Several earlier reagents, such as dibenzoylmethane⁷, 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-benzoyl-pyrazol-5-one⁸, thenoyltrifluoroacetone⁴ and disodium-1,2-dihydroxybenzene-3,5-disulphonate⁹ are still used for their determination. These methods operate in either nonaqueous media or the sensitivity is rather low. The application of PAN, for detection of metal ions in chemical analysis, has been extensively investigated in the past several years^{4,7,8,10,11}. However, little work has been reported, on the systematic studies of Nd^{3+} -PAN or Sm^{3+} -PAN complexes, in the presence of micelles. Therefore, we have taken up the study of determination of Nd^{3+} , Sm^{3+} with PAN, in different micellar media which would enable one to determine these metal ions in trace levels.

Experimental

Reagents and apparatus :

All absorbance measurements and the spectra of Nd^{3+} / Sm^{3+} -PAN complex solutions were taken at 30 °C with

a double beam UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Shimadzu 1800). Measurements of pH were made using control dynamics digital pH meter equipped with a glass electrode. Doubly distilled water was used to prepare all the solutions. All reagents used were of analytical grade. CTAB, SDS, Triton X-100 (Merck) were used without further purification. PAN (Reidal) solution as 0.01 mol dm^{-3} stock was prepared by dissolving appropriate amount in the respective surfactant solution and was then standardized⁷. For example, $0.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of PAN was prepared by dissolving in $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of surfactant solution. Standard 0.01 mol dm^{-3} of Nd^{3+} solution was prepared by dissolving appropriate amount of the oxide in 1 : 3 nitric acid. Solutions were heated on a sand bath until the dissolution of oxides and diluted with water to the mark in volumetric flasks. The stock solution was then standardized¹². Buffer solution of pH 6–8 (borax) and 8–10 (ammonical) were prepared according to NBS for the absorption characteristics over the range of wavelengths studied.

Analytical procedure :

A typical experiment was carried out as follows :

A $0.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ PAN in surfactant, 10 ml of buffer (pH 9.2) and $0.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of $\text{Nd}^{3+}/\text{Sm}^{3+}$ solution were added and allowed to stand for 20 min in a 25 ml flask with doubly distilled water. Absorbance was measured against a reagent blank ($0.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ PAN in surfactant, 10 ml of buffer solution, in 25 ml flask) at 545 nm, 535 nm, 540 nm in CTAB, Triton-X, SDS respectively.

Results and discussion

Absorption spectra of the complex :

Absorption spectra of the metal-PAN complex were taken at the optimum conditions ($0.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of $\text{Nd}^{3+}/\text{Sm}^{3+}$, $0.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of PAN in $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of surfactant and buffer pH of 9.2) in the micellar media against PAN reagent as blank (Fig. 1). The absorption spectra shows a maxima at 545 nm, 535 nm, 540 nm in CTAB, Triton-X, SDS. PAN reagent shows a maximum at 472 nm. Absorbance is higher in the case of non-ionic surfactant compared to cationic or anionic.

Time of stability :

Absorbance of the complex solution was measured at various timings and the complex was found to be stable for 24 h as against the complex in aqueous media where it is stable only for 30 min¹³.

Optimization of conditions :

Effect of pH :

The effects of various parameters on the sensitivity of $\text{Nd}^{3+}/\text{Sm}^{3+}$ determination were investigated one at a time; quantization procedure was evaluated for obtaining optimum condition. pH is one of the most important parameters for this determination as the complex formation depends largely on the pH. The optimum pH for the formation of $\text{Nd}^{3+}/\text{Sm}^{3+}$ -PAN complex is in the range of 8.5–9.5 (Figs. 2a/2b). The pH was adjusted with ammonium chloride-ammonium hydroxide buffer. The complexation was favored in weakly basic conditions. In the

Fig. 1. Visible spectra of (a) Nd^{3+} and (b) Sm^{3+} -PAN complexes in CTAB, SDS and Triton-X. [Metal] = $0.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, [PAN] = $0.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and [surfactant] = $2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH = 9.20.

Fig. 2a. Effect of pH on the absorbance of Nd^{3+} -PAN complex in the three micellar media. $[\text{Nd}^{3+}] = 0.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{PAN}] = 0.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{surfactant}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Fig. 2b. Effect of pH on the absorbance of Sm^{3+} -PAN complex in the three micellar media. $[\text{Sm}^{3+}] = 0.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{PAN}] = 0.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{surfactant}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

presence of non-ionic surfactants, rather wide optimal pH ranges and high absorption intensities are observed. In the presence of anionic and cationic surfactants, both complexes exhibit equally narrow pH ranges of complexation, which are slightly shifted to a more alkaline region. Based on these observations, other investigations were carried out at pH 9.2.

Effect of PAN concentration :

The effect of concentration of the chelating reagent PAN was studied, for the metal to ligand ratio between 1 : 1 to 1 : 20 at pH 9.2 (by varying the PAN concentration from $5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ to $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and keeping CTAB concentration $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and metal ion at $0.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. Absorbance of $\text{Nd}^{3+}/\text{Sm}^{3+}$ -PAN surfactant has been found to increase with increase in the concentration of the ligand. As the ligand absorbs significantly at λ_{max} of the complex, the increase in absorbance is partly due to the increase in the ligand concentration. Absorbance values were, therefore, corrected for the absorption of the uncomplexed ligand and plotted against its molar ratio. The plot shows a sharp increase up to 10.0 (L : M) and remains practically constant for 20.0 and above. During subsequent studies the ligand concentration was kept ten times the metal concentration wherever possible. The sensitivity was maximum and constant above a concentration of PAN $0.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (Figs. 3a/3b). This suggests a total complexation at this concentration.

Fig. 3a. Effect of $[\text{PAN}]$ on the absorbance of Nd^{3+} -PAN complex in the three micellar media. $[\text{Nd}^{3+}] = 0.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{surfactant}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH = 9.2.

Effect of micelles :

All the three kinds of surfactants, sodium dodecyl sulphate (anionic), cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (cationic) and Triton X-100 (non-ionic) were investigated to

Fig. 3b. Effect of [PAN] on the absorbance of Sm^{3+} -PAN complex in the three micellar media $[\text{Sm}^{3+}] = 0.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{surfactant}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 9.2$

Fig. 4b. Effect of [surfactant] on the absorbance of Sm^{3+} -PAN complex in the three micellar media. $[\text{Sm}^{3+}] = 0.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 9.2$.

determine their impact on absorption profiles of $\text{Nd}^{3+}/\text{Sm}^{3+}$ -PAN complex. The effect of surfactant concentration was studied within the range from $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ to $2.4 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (Figs. 4a/4b). The micellar solutions of ionic surfactants enable formation of several ternary species of different optical properties which are dependent on pH, concentration of the reagent and the surfactant. Non-ionic surfactants cause significant change in the optical properties and stabilities of the complex formed.

Fig. 4a. Effect of [surfactant] on the absorbance of Nd^{3+} -PAN complex in the three micellar media $[\text{Nd}^{3+}] = 0.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 9.2$.

The relative change in the absorbance on complexation in case of anionic surfactant was low as compared to the cationic and non-ionic surfactants. This is attributed to the attractive forces between the negative head of micelles and the positive charge of metal ions, which causes lower apparent constant between metal ions and ligands^{14,15}.

The absorbance at λ_{max} of the complex shows a sharp increase with increasing [surfactant]. The absorbance-[surfactant] profile has a maximum. The increase in the absorbance value in the presence of micelle is due to the binding of the reactants in a small volume of stern layer of the micelle, thus leading to considerable concentration effect. Further, studies¹⁶ reveal that the maximum in the absorbance-[surfactant] profile is produced by two opposing effects. Binding of reactants in the stern layer begins and they are transferred into small volume of the micellar pseudophase. There is thus a concentration effect which is responsible for increase in absorbance. This concentration effect is opposed by continuous dilution of the reactants within the micellar pseudophase with increasing surfactant concentration. The former effect is predominant at lower surfactant concentration, whereas the later becomes important at higher concentrations of surfactant resulting in maximum in the absorbance-[surfactant] profile. The decrease, observed at higher con-

centration can also be due to the decrease in the number of chromophores per micelle.

The sensitivity and molar extinction coefficient were studied for all three surfactants (Table 1). The results show that the molar extinction coefficient is more in the case of Triton-X than CTAB or SDS.

Table 1. Molar absorptivity and Sandells sensitivity values for Nd³⁺/Sm³⁺-PAN complex in the three surfactants

Surfactant	Molar absorptivity (mol dm ³ cm ⁻¹)		Sandells sensitivity (µg/cm ²)	
	Nd ³⁺	Sm ³⁺	Nd ³⁺	Sm ³⁺
CTAB	4.4 × 10 ⁴	5.8 × 10 ⁴	2.96 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.37 × 10 ⁻⁴
Triton-X	6.2 × 10 ⁴	7.4 × 10 ⁴	3.02 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.80 × 10 ⁻⁴
SDS	4.3 × 10 ⁴	5.7 × 10 ⁴	2.17 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.37 × 10 ⁻⁴

The binding constant for the chelating agent PAN was calculated in all the three micelles by taking absorbance of the complex solution at different surfactant concentration above CMC and under the conditions [Surfactant] >> [PAN] using the following equation¹⁷,

$$1/(A_M - A_w^0) = 1/(A_M^0 - A_w^0) \times (1 + 1/K_s C)$$

where A_M⁰ is the limiting absorbance in the presence of micelles, A_w⁰ the absorbance in the absence of surfactant and A_M the absorbance in the presence of micelles. The binding constant was found to be 104 dm³ mol⁻¹ in Triton-X, 100 dm³ mol⁻¹ in CTAB and 84 dm³ mol⁻¹ in SDS. The higher value of binding constant in presence of Triton-X is indicative of higher sensitivity and molar absorptivity.

Stoichiometry, sensitivity and detection limits :

The empirical formula of the complex of Nd³⁺/Sm³⁺-PAN complex was determined by adopting the Jobs continuous variation method¹⁸ and further confirmed from mole ratio method. The results suggests that a metal complex molar ratio of 1 : 3 is formed (Fig. 4). Calibration graph for the determination of Nd³⁺/Sm³⁺ was plotted over the range of 1 × 10⁻⁶ mol dm⁻³ to 3 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³ of Nd³⁺/Sm³⁺ the calibration graph obtained was straight line passing through the origin and the molar absorptivity was calculated (Table 1). The Sandells sensitivity¹⁹ was calculated and found to be 2.96 × 10⁻⁴, 3.02 × 10⁻⁴, 2.17 × 10⁻⁴ µg cm⁻² for Nd³⁺ and 2.37 × 10⁻⁴, 1.8 × 10⁻⁴, 2.37 × 10⁻⁴ µg cm⁻² for Sm³⁺ in CTAB,

Triton-X and SDS. These results showed an increase in sensitivity when compared to the aqueous media¹³. Precision of the methods was also determined from ten replicate concentration measurements on standard solutions of Nd³⁺/Sm³⁺.

Relative standard deviation was found to be 1.54, 0.514, 1.28 for Nd³⁺ and 1.57, .602, 1.29 for Sm³⁺ in CTAB, Triton-X, SDS respectively, for 0.5 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³ of Nd³⁺/Sm³⁺. Absorption measurements at λ_{max}, are recommended for the determination of Nd³⁺/Sm³⁺ ions with PAN in the neutral, cationic and anionic micellar medium. Recommended wavelengths shows, better sensitivity and precision.

Effect of foreign ions :

The effect of presence of foreign ions on the trace level determination of Nd³⁺/Sm³⁺ in aqueous phase has been investigated. The criterion for the studies was ±4.0% change in absorbance. The amount of foreign ion tolerated (i.e. which changes absorbance by ±4.0%) is given in the Table 2; ions of Fe^{III}, Cd^{II}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} and U^{VI} interfere. The complexation reaction between Nd³⁺/Sm³⁺-PAN is completely masked by EDTA, citrate, phosphate at low concentrations, whereas oxalates, tartarates, Br⁻, Cl⁻, I⁻, and SCN⁻ are negligible at the given concentrations.

Table 2. Effect of foreign ions on the Nd³⁺/Sm³⁺-PAN complex in the three surfactants

Foreign ions	Molar tolerance limit (ion)/(Ln ^{III}) in
	CTAB, Triton-X, SDS
NO ₃ ⁻ , ClO ₄ ⁻ , Br ⁻ , Cl ⁻ , I ⁻ and SCN ⁻	>2000
Ca ^{II} , Mg ^{II} , Mo ^{VI} , Cr ^{VI}	>2000
Oxalates, V ^V	≥ 100
F ⁻	≥ 50
Acetate, tartarate, thorium	≥ 10
Uranyl(VI), Al ³⁺ , citrate,	Equal
phosphate, Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Fe ^{III}	

Conclusion :

One of the most important aspects of the present work is the simple and rapid detection and trace level determination of Nd/Sm ions in an aqueous solution of a surfactant. The sensitivity and selectivity were considerably improved in presence of micelles. The method does not

require tedious and expensive process of solvent extraction, hence avoiding the use of expensive toxic and carcinogenic organic solvents. The method is not only sensitive but also economical (since it is cheaper than ICP-AES, and AAS and does not require any gas or maintenance) and less complicated.

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